

Determination of the Total Phenolic Contents of Essential Oil Obtained from *Cymbopogon Citratus* (Lemongrass) and *Persea Americana Mill* (Avocado Pear Seed) and its Bioactive Component Using Gc-MS Analysis

George C. Njoku^{1*}, Chibuzo V. Alisigwe², David U. Iloanusi¹ and Prisca C. Aririguzo³

¹Department of Biochemistry, College of Natural Sciences, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria.

²Department of Microbiology, College of Natural Sciences, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria.

³Department of Public Health, School of Health Technology, Federal University of Technology Owerri P.M.B 1526, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

Abstract :-

Background and Purpose: Essential oils are a mixture of volatile lipophilic constituents, most commonly sourced from leaf, bark tissue of higher plants. The study investigated the total phenolic contents of essential oil obtained from *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemongrass) and *Persea Americana mill* (avocado pear seed) and its bioactive component.

Methods: The essential oils of both plants were obtained using the Soxhlet extraction method. Total phenol compositions were assayed using standard colourimetric methods. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis was used to ascertain the presence of phytochemicals in the extract.

Results: The total phenolic content of the plants showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference ranging from 23.88 to 46.38 mg tannic acid equivalent/g of extract. *Cymbopogon citratus* had the highest value of 46.38 ± 0.26 mg tannic acid equivalent/g compared to *Persea Americana Mill's*, which had a value of 23.88 ± 0.34 mg tannic acid equivalent/g. The chromatograms corresponding to the chromatographic analysis (GC-MS) of *Cymbopogon citratus* and *Persea Americana Mill* allowed the identification of 26 different compounds from *Cymbopogon citratus* 15 different compounds from *Persea Americana Mill*. The peak height of *Cymbopogon citratus* showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference ranging from 2781 to 335638. It was observed that Caryophyllene had the highest value compared to that of Myrcenyl acetate, which had the lowest value of 2781. *Persea Americana mill* also showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference ranging from 560862 to 13557730, with Tetra decanoic acid having the highest value of 13557730 compared to 1 E-11, Z-13-Octadecatriene with the lowest value of 560862. This difference in peak height could result from the difference in the molecular weight of the volatile compounds.

Conclusions: Overall, the study gave information on the phenolic and volatile compounds of *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemongrass) and *Persea Americana mill* (avocado pear seed) and could be a potential source of natural

antioxidants and could be used as a therapeutic agent in preventing or treating degenerative diseases associated with oxidative stress.

Keywords:- Essential Oils, *Cymbopogon citratus*, *Persea Americana mill*, Gas-Chromatography Mass-Spectrophotometry (GC-MS).

I. INTRODUCTION

There has been an increased search for food substances with health benefits. Such foods contain bioactive components that are advantageous to human health and exhibit properties as inhibitors of the dreaded COVID-19 main protease (Galanakis, 2020). Plants do not just provide food and shelter, oxygen, and beautification to animals but are also sources of phytomedicines. The pharmaceutical industry has identified these bio-active agents in plants and their importance in synthetic medicine and has tested the most commonly used plant species (Nguenang *et al.*, 2005; Khan *et al.*, 2009). Phytomedicines are very beneficial and recently occupied an important place in medicine and plant research (Roger *et al.*, 2015). The medicinal property of plants results from bioactive phytochemicals that they contain (Sheikh *et al.*, 2013). Liu (2004) defined these bioactive non-nutrient plant compounds as phytochemicals.

Cymbopogon citratus (lemongrass) and *Persea Americana mill* (Avacado pear seed) have been shown to contain these bioactive compounds and utilized in food, cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries. Lemongrass is a tall perennial grass generally grown in humid tropical and subtropical regions belonging to *Poaceae* (Olorunnisola *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, lemongrass contains high amounts of minerals, vitamins and macronutrients. In Nigeria, lemongrass is commonly used as spices and contains phenolic compounds that possess solid antioxidant capacity (Vazquez-Briones *et al.*, 2015). These phenolic compounds contain the benzene ring with a substituted hydroxyl group with a high radical scavenging capacity. They are the most produced

secondary metabolite in plants, whose distribution is shown throughout the metabolic process. Numerous compounds, including flavonoids, phenolic acids, complex flavonoids, and coloured anthocyanins, are phenolic substances or polyphenols (Babbar *et al.*, 2014). Apart from the defence, which is the function usually associated with these compounds, they also play other vital roles like incorporating attractive substances to accelerate pollination, antibacterial and antifungal activities as well as defence against herbivores (Alasalvar *et al.*, 2001; Acamovic and Brooker, 2005; Edreva *et al.*, 2008).

Like *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemongrass), studies have shown that *Persea Americana mill*, a dicotyledonous plant from the Lauraceae, is mainly consumed as fresh fruit can be commercialized to give a higher added value product including bioactive compounds (Bruno *et al.*, 2018). These bioactive compounds of avocado, which have beneficial effects on human health, include vitamin C, vitamin E, carotenoids and phenolic compounds. The seeds and peels considered wastes are good sources of antioxidants (Saavedra *et al.*, 2017; Ayala-Zavala *et al.*, 2011) capable of preventing inflammatory diseases. Therefore, the pulp of avocado is an important raw material for the food, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries (Bruno *et al.*, 2018).

This study aims at the determination of total phenolic contents of essential oil obtained from *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemongrass) and *Persea Americana mill* (avocado pear seed) and its bioactive component using GC-MS analysis.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Collection and preparation of plant sample

The fresh *Cymbopogon citratus* (Lemongrass) plant and *Persea Americana Mill* (Avocado Pear) was collected from uncultivated farmland at Amanwo community in Ikwuano Local Government Area of Abia State. The plant was authenticated by a Taxonomist (Dr Ibe K. Ndukwe) from the forestry department, College of Natural Resources and Environment Management (CNREM), Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike (Specimen voucher number = IHF 23142). The fresh leaves were washed thoroughly under running tap water and air-dried for three weeks (21 days) at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). The dried leaves were grounded to a fine powder using a heavy-duty grinding machine (TSK-948 West Point, France) and stored in a tight-lid container pending its use.

B. Extraction of plant material

The extraction was carried out using the Soxhlet apparatus at 40°C with n-hexane as the solvent under reflux for 6 hours. The set-up was allowed to reflux until all the compounds were collected.

The extract was transferred to a sterile clean container and stored at 4°C in a refrigerator until further analysis.

C. Determination of total phenolic content (TPC)

The total phenolic content (TPC) was determined colourimetrically using Folin–Ciocalteu reagent, as described by Paško *et al.* (2009). Methanolic solution of the extract in the concentration of 10 mg/ml was used in the analysis. The reaction mixture was prepared by mixing 0.5 ml of methanolic extract solution, 2.5 ml of 10% Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent dissolved in water and 2.5 ml 7.5% NaHCO_3 . After that, a blank solution was made, which contained 0.5 ml methanol, 2.5 ml 10% Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent dissolved in water and 2.5 ml of 7.5% of NaHCO_3 . Both samples and blank were incubated in a thermostat at 45°C for 45 min. The absorbance was determined using a spectrophotometer at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 765 \text{ nm}$. Mean absorbance value was obtained when the samples were prepared in triplicate. The same procedure was repeated for the standard solution of Gallic acid. The concentration of phenolic was read from the calibration line, and then the content in extracts from the measured absorbance was expressed in terms of Gallic acid equivalent (mg of GA/g of extract).

D. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis

An Agilent 6890N gas chromatography equipped with an autosampler connected to an Agilent Mass Spectrophotometric Detector was used. One micro-litre of the sample was injected in the pulsed spitless mode onto a 30m x 0.25mm ID DB 5MS coated fused silica column with a film thickness of 0.15 micrometre. Helium gas was used as a carrier gas, and the column head pressure was maintained at 20psi to give a constant of 1ml/min. Other operating conditions were preset. The column temperature was initially held at 55°C for 0.4min, increased to 200°C at a rate of $25^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, then to 280°C at a rate of $8^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and to a final temperature of 300°C at a rate of $25^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, held for 2mins. The identification time was based on retention time, and components with lower retention time elute first before higher retention time.

III. RESULTS

From our table below, the total phenolic content present in our leaves extract of *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemongrass) plants showed 46.38 ± 0.26 (mg TAequ./g) and avocado (*Persea Americana Mill*) pear seed showed 23.88 ± 0.34 (mg TAequ./g), both were expressed in terms of tannic acid equivalent and the values obtained for the concentration of total are expressed as mg of Ta/g of the extract.

Table. 1: Total phenolic contents of EOCC (*Cymbopogon citratus*) and EOPAM (*Persea Americana Mill*) leaves

Plants	Total Phenols (mg TAequ. /g)
Lemongrass	46.38 ± 0.26
Avocado pear seed	23.88 ± 0.34

EOS=Essential Oil *Cymbopogon citratus*, EOPAM=Essential Oil *Persea Americana Mill* leaves, TAE = tannic acid equivalent; GAE = gallic acid equivalent

A. GCMS Screening of The EOCC (*Cymbopogon citratus*).

The GC-MS total ion content (TIC) chromatograms of the 26 peaks of the compounds detected are shown in Figure 1. The various chemical compounds present in the essential oils obtained from *Cymbopogon citratus* leaves using the Soxhlet extraction method with n-hexane solvent is presented in table 2 below. The mass spectrums of the major

compounds are shown in Figures 2 – 6, while the structures are shown in Figures 7 – 31. The structures of the major compounds detected were Myrcenyl acetate (9.703%), Caryophyllene (8.997%), 4-Terpinenyl acetate (7.579%), Citronellal (6.383%) and 4-Androsten-3 β ,6 β -diol-17-one (5.829%).

Fig. 1: GC-MS chromatogram of *Cymbopogon citratus* methanol leaves extract

Table 2: Chemical composition (GC-MS) of the n-hexane extract of *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemongrass)

Name	Peak Height (pA)	Retention time (minutes)	Conc (%)	Formular
2,6-Octadienal,3,7-dimethyl-, (E)	4314	4.560	3.720	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O
2,6-Octadienal,3,7-dimethyl-, (Z)	3201	4.922	2.522	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O
2,6-Octadien-1-ol,3,7-dimethyl-, (Z)	7541	5.550	1.127	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O
Geranyl oleate	3815	5.612	0.845	C ₂₈ H ₅₀ O ₂
Citronellal	21685	6.120	6.383	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O
Cyclohexene,1-methyl-4-(1-methylethylidene)	21741	6.710	2.577	C ₁₀ H ₁₆
Geranyl acetate	32428	6.804	4.943	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₂
Myrcenyl acetate	2781	7.079	9.703	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₂
4-Terpinenyl acetate	4151	7.308	7.579	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₂
2-Nonanone	6364	7.914	1.652	C ₉ H ₁₈ O
endo-Borneol	6452	8.080	3.662	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O
Linalyl acetate	8726	8.257	2.468	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₂
α -Pinene	3010	8.395	0.514	C ₁₀ H ₁₆
β -Pinene	7338	11.445	1.142	C ₁₀ H ₁₆
Limonene	2887	11.891	0.504	C ₁₀ H ₁₆
Linalool	4085	12.154	0.548	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O
Caryophyllene	335638	15.364	8.997	C ₁₅ H ₂₄
Bicyclo(7.2.0)undec-4-ene, 4,11,11-trimethyl-8-methylene-, [1R*(1R*,4Z,9S*)]	2958	16.056	0.584	C ₁₅ H ₂₄
Fenitrothion	6078	17.475	1.004	C ₉ H ₁₂ NO ₅ PS
Methyl parathion	4064	17.790	0.625	C ₈ H ₁₀ NO ₅ PS
Retinol	8319	17.830	1.194	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ O
6-Beta-hydroperoxy-3alpha,5-cyclo-5alpha-androstan-17-one	3470	17.962	0.659	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₃
4-Androsten-3 β ,6 β -diol-17-one	29747	18.042	5.829	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₃
3 β ,5 α ,6 β -Trihydroxyandrostan-17-one	7885	19.821	1.260	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ O ₄
δ 5-Androsten-3,17-dione	4185	20.331	0.659	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ O ₂

Fig. 2: Myrcenylacetat

Fig. 3: Caryophyllene

Fig. 4: 4-Terpinenyl acetate

Fig. 5: Citronellal

Fig. 6: 4-Androsten-3 β ,6 β -diol-17-one

Fig. 7: 2,6-Octadienal, 3,7-dimethyl-, (E)-

Fig. 10: Geranyl oleate

Fig. 8: 2,6-Octadienal, 3,7-dimethyl-, (Z)-

Fig. 11: Citronellal

Fig. 9: 2,6-Octadien-1-ol, 3,7-dimethyl-, (Z)-

Fig. 12: Cyclohexene, 1-methyl-4-(1-methylethylidene)-

Fig. 13: Geranyl acetate

Fig. 14: Myrcenylacetat

Fig. 15: 4-Terpinenyl acetate

Fig. 16: 2-Nonanone

Fig. 17: endo-Borneol

Fig. 18: Linalyl acetate

Fig. 19: α -Pinene

Fig. 20: β -Pinene

Fig. 21: Limonene

Fig. 22: Linalool

Fig. 23: Caryophyllene

Fig. 24: Bicyclo[7.2.0]undec-4-ene, 4,11,11-trimethyl-8-methylene-, [1R-(1R*,4Z,9S*)]-

Fig. 25: Fenitrothion

Fig. 26: Methyl parathion

Fig. 27: Retinol

Fig. 28: 6Beta-hydroperoxy-3alpha,5-cyclo-5alpha-androstan-17-one

Fig. 29: 4-Androsten-3β,6β-diol-17-one

Fig. 30: 3β,5α,6β-Trihydroxyandrostan-17-one

Fig. 31: δ5-Androsten-3,17-dione

B. GCMS Screening of EOPAM (*Persea Americana Mill*) leaves,

The GC-MS total ion content (TIC) chromatograms of the 15 peaks of the compounds detected are shown in Figure 32. The various chemical compounds present in the essential oils obtained from *Persea Americana Mill* leaves using the Soxhlet extraction method with n-hexane solvent is presented

in table 2 below. The mass spectrums of the major compounds are shown in Figures 33 – 35, while the structures are shown in Figures 36 – 49. The structures of the major compounds detected were Tetradecanoic acid (33.326%), 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester (20.122%), and Oleic acid (11.60%).

Fig. 32: GC-MS chromatogram of *Persea Americana Mill* methanol leaves extract

Table 3: Chemical composition (GC-MS) of the n-hexane extract of *Persea Americana Mill* (Avocado pear)

Name	Peak-Height (pA)	Retention time (minutes)	Conc (%)	Formular
Dodecanoic acid	2108314	1.417	3.959	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂
Tetra decanoic acid	13557730	1.545	33.326	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂
n-Hexadecenoic acid	5008226	1.984	7.065	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O ₂
9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester	3592155	3.792	20.122	C ₁₉ H ₃₄ O ₂
11-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester	595510	4.654	1.080	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₂
Oleic acid	3497450	7.892	11.600	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂
9,12-Octadecadien-1-ol, (Z, Z)-	925530	12.430	2.310	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O
1, E-11, Z-13-Octadecatriene	560862	20.403	1.400	C ₁₈ H ₃₂
E-11(12-Cyclopropyl) dodecen-1-ol	870487	26.124	1.223	C ₁₅ H ₂₈
Undecylenic acid	1444111	28.987	1.922	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ O ₂
1-Dodecanol	1745352	30.230	2.325	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ O
Palmitaldehyde, disopentyl acetal	1836858	31.397	2.332	C ₂₆ H ₅₄ O ₂
9-Octadecenal	1836858	32.497	3.321	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O
(E)-13-Docosenoic acid	2735597	33.540	3.720	C ₂₂ H ₄₂ O ₂
Erucic acid	2276684	34.690	3.246	C ₂₂ H ₄₂ O ₂

Fig. 33: Tetradeconoic acid

Fig. 34: 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid

Fig. 35: Oleic Acid

Fig. 36: Dodecanoic acid

Fig. 37: Tetradecanoic acid

Fig. 38: n-Hexadecanoic acid

Fig. 39: 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester

Fig. 40: 11-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester

Fig. 41: Oleic Acid

Fig. 42: 1, E-11, Z-13-Octadecatriene

Fig. 43: E-11(12-Cyclopropyl) dodecen-1-ol

Fig. 44: Undecylenic acid

Fig. 45: 1-Dodecanol

Fig. 46: Palmitaldehyde, diisopentyl acetal

Fig. 47: 9-Octadecenal

Fig. 48: (E)-13-Docosenoic acid

Fig. 49: Erucic acid

IV. DISCUSSION

Medicinal plants have a recognized medicinal purpose, ranging from plants used in traditional pharmaceutical production to plants used in herbal medicine preparations values (Mohammed *et al.*, 2012). The medicinal effects of plants are due to metabolites, especially secondary compounds produced by plant species. The phenolic compound has been considered the largest category of phytochemicals studied for its antioxidant properties and have a wide range of health benefits, including anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetic effects (Hamzah *et al.*, 2013). *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemongrass) and *Persea Americana mill* (Avacado pear seed) contain these secondary compounds utilized in foods, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries. Hence, this study investigated the total phenolic content in *Cymbopogon citratus*, *Persea Americana Mill*, and the bioactive compound present in the n-hexane extract using Gas chromatography and Mass spectroscopy.

The total phenolic content of the plants under review showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference ranging from 23.88 to 46.38 mg tannic acid equivalent/g of extract. *Cymbopogon citratus* had the highest value of 46.38 ± 0.26 mg tannic acid equivalent/g compared to *Persea Americana Mill's*, which had a value of 23.88 ± 0.34 mg tannic acid equivalent/g. The difference in phenolic content could be due to the type of soil the plants were planted on or climatic conditions. Since phenols are studied for their antioxidant properties against oxidative damage or stress (Mandal *et al.*, 2010) and generally, increased phenolic and flavonoids concentration of plant extract correlates with increased antioxidant activity. Patel *et al.* (2010) reported that the root of *L. schimperi*, compared to the other tested samples, showed a relatively low number of secondary metabolites as leaves of *R. Abyssinia* and *H. insignis*. This result is in agreement with the findings of the present study.

The GC-MS analysis of n-hexane extract of *Cymbopogon citratus* and *Persea Americana Mill* revealed that the plant contained a wide range of photo-compounds which may be responsible for its therapeutic potentials. The active principles with their retention times (RT) and total peak area (%) in the chromatogram of each constituent that was identified in the fixed oil obtained from the species depicted twenty-five peaks and fifteen peaks, and this implies the presence of twenty-five (25) phytol-compounds and fifteen (15) phytol-compounds in the extract. The identified phytol-compounds comprise mainly hydrocarbons, fatty acids, alcohols, esters and phenols.

Figure 1 and 32 shows the chromatograms corresponding to the chromatographic analysis (GC-MS) of *Cymbopogon citratus* and *Persea Americana mill*, which allowed the identification of 26 different compounds from *Cymbopogon citratus* and 15 different compounds from *Persea Americana mill*, of which the major compounds identified were Myrcenyl acetate (9.703%), 4-Terpinenyl acetate (7.579%), Citronellal (6.383%), 4-Androsten-3 β ,6 β -diol-17-one (5.829%), Tetradecanoic acid (33.326%), 9,12-

Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester (20.122%), and Oleic acid (11.600).

The result of the peak height of *Cymbopogon citratus* showed that there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference ranging from 2781 to 335638. It was observed that Caryophyllene had the highest value compared to that of Myrcenyl acetate, which had the lowest value of 2781. This difference in peak height could result from the difference in the molecular weight of the volatile compounds. The result of the retention time showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference ranging from 4.560 minutes to 20.331minutes. This difference can result from molecular weight, which may also determine the migration capability of the volatile compounds.

The result of the peak height of the volatile compounds found in the *Persea Americana mill* showed that there is a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference ranging from 560862 to 13557730, with Tetra decanoic acid having the highest value of 13557730 compared to that of 1, E-11, Z-13-Octadecatriene with the lowest value of 560862. The retention time result also revealed a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference ranging from 1.417 minutes to 34.690 minutes, with Erucic acid having the highest value and Dodecanoic acid having the lowest value. Identifying these phyto-compounds by GC-MS is a valuable technique in suggesting the potential curative properties of plants (McGaw *et al.*, 2002).

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

➤ Conclusion

This study showed that *Cymbopogon citratus* and *Persea Americana Mill*, based on their total phenolic presence and the phytochemicals obtained through our GC/MS, could be a potential source of natural antioxidants that could be used as a therapeutic agent in preventing or treatment of degenerative diseases associated with oxidative stress.

➤ Recommendation

Already existing literature has shown that the pharmacological effects of plants are a result of the therapeutic activities of their active compounds, of which phenols are vital components. The present study has shown that the essential oil extracted from avocado pear seed and lemon grass contains a significant number of phenols, pointing to the possibility of the efficacy of these oils in exhibiting therapeutic effects. Hence, these essential oils can be used to treat various illnesses that are treatable with phenols. It is suggested that further studies be carried out to ascertain the safety of these oils when used by humans.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Acamovic, T. and Brooker, J. D. (2005). Biochemistry of plant secondary metabolites and their effects in animals. *Proceedings of Nutritional Society*. 64, 403–412.
- [2]. Alasalvar, C., Grigor, J. M., Zhang, D. L., Quantick, P. C. and Shahidi, F. (2001). Comparison of volatiles,

- phenolics, sugars, antioxidant vitamins, and sensory quality of different colored carrot varieties. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 49, 1410–1416.
- [3]. Ayala-Zavala, J. F., V. Vega-Vega, C. Rosas-Dominguez, H. Palafox-Carlos and Villa-Rodriguez, J.A. (2011). Agro-industrial potential of exotic fruit byproducts as a source of food additives. *Food Research International Journal*. 44: 1866-1874.
- [4]. Babbar, N., Oberoi, H. S., Sandhu, S. K. and Bhargav, V. K. (2014). Influence of different solvents in extraction of phenolic compounds from vegetable residues and their evaluation as natural sources of antioxidants. *Journal of food science and technology*. 51, 2568–2575.
- [5]. Bruno M., Maria I. D., Ana C., Marina S., Esperanza M., Antonio D., Lillian B. and Isabel C. (2018). Bioactive characterization of *Persea americana* Mill. by-products: A rich source of inherent antioxidants. *Industrial Crops and Products*. 111: 212-218
- [6]. Edreva, A., Velikova, V., Tsonev, T., Dagnon, S., Gürel, A. L. and Aktas, L. (2008). Stress-protective role of secondary metabolites: Diversity of functions and mechanisms. *General and Applied Plant Physiology*. 34, 67–78.
- [7]. Galanakis (2020). The food system in the era of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic crisis. *Foods*. 9, 523.
- [8]. Hamzah, R. U., Egwim, E.C., Kabiru, A.Y. and Muazu, M. B. (2013) Phytochemical and in vitro antioxidant properties of the methanolic extract of fruits of *Blighia sapida*, *Vitellaria paradoxa* and *Vitex doniana*. *Oxidative Antioxidant Medical Science*, 2(3), 215-221.
- [9]. Khan S., Chattopadhyay M. T., Sarkar D., Chatterjee M. C., Sharma T., Dey R., Bag P. and Chakraborti P. (2009). Recent advancements for the evaluation of antiviral activities of natural products. *New Biotechnology*. 25(5):347–368.
- [10]. McGaw, L.J., Jagar, A.K. and van Staden, J. (2002). Isolation of antibacterial fatty acids from *Schotia brachypetala*. *Fitoterapia*, 3: 431-433.
- [11]. Mohammed, M., Aboki, M.A., Saidu, H.M., Victor, O., Tawakalitu, A. and Maikano, S.A. (2012). Phytochemical and Some Antimicrobial Activity of *Cassia Occidentalis* L. (Caesalpinaceae). *International Journal of Science Technology*. 2(4).
- [12]. Nguenang G. M., Tsabang N., Nkongmeneck B. and Fongzossie E. (2005). Simple plan of management of the Community forests in Cameroon: futurology for the natural resources rational management: case of *Enantia chlorantha* Oliv. (Annonaceae) Cameroon Journal of Ethnobotany. 1:76–81.
- [13]. Olorunnisola, S. K., Asiyebi, H. T., Hammed, A. M. and Simsek, S. (2014). Biological properties of lemongrass: an overview. *International Food Research Journal*.
- [14]. Paško, P., Bartoń, H., Zagrodzki, P., Gorinstein, S., Fołta, M., and Zachwieja, Z. (2009). Anthocyanins, total polyphenols and antioxidant activity in amaranth and quinoa seeds and sprouts during their growth. *Food Chemistry*. 115: 994-998.
- [15]. Patel, A., Patel, A. and Patel, N. (2010). Estimation of flavonoid, polyphenolic content and in-vitro antioxidant capacity of leaves *Tephrosin purpurea* Linn. (Leguminosae), *International journal of pharmacological sciences and research*, 1(1):66-77
- [16]. Rui Hai Liu (2004). Potential Synergy of Phytochemicals in Cancer Prevention: Mechanism of Action, *The Journal of Nutrition*, 134: 3479S–3485S,
- [17]. Saavedra, J., Cordova, A., Navarro, R., Diaz-Calderon, P. and Fuentealba C. (2017). Industrial avocado waste: Functional compounds preservation by convective drying process. *Journal of Food Engineering*. 198: 81-90.
- [18]. Vazquez-Briones, Hernandez I. R. and Guerrero-Beltran J. A. (2015). *Journal of Food Research*. 4 (3): 36-45.